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- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
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- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti metodistining boshqaruv funksiyalari.....	10
Qarshibayeva Dilfuza Xidirbayevna	
Texnologik mashinalar va jihozlar ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarida kasbiy kompetensiyani shakllantirishning pedagogik qonuniyatlari va metodologik tizimini ishlab chiqish	15
Elmanov Abbas Begmat o'g'li, Mirzaumidov Asilbek Shuxratjonovich	
Katta yoshdagi guruh bolalarida o'z-o'zini boshqarish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda o'yinning roli	19
Ergasheva Farangiz Umidjon qizi, Fayzullayev Sharipboy Nurillayevich	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida ekologik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning dolzarbligi.....	23
Yaxshiboyeva Nargiza Rustamqulovna	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida inson resurslarini boshqarishda muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimidan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari	28
Gulmira Jumanova	
Nomoddiy madaniy merosning talaba-yoshlarni yuksak ma'naviyatli shaxs sifatida tarbiyalashdagi ahamiyati	33
Erboyev Suxrob Abdusalomovich	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar va ularda hissiy-irodaning shakllanishi	37
Davlatova Zebo Haydarovna	
Zamonaviy oilada avlodlararo munosabatlarning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	40
Ochilova Farida Baxriddinovna	
Maktab va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida qizlar kitobxonligini rivojlantirish metodlari	44
Qo'chqarova Oysha Oltibayevna	
Buyuk allomalar merosidan foydalanishning metodik holati va mavjud muammolari.....	48
Sevara Mamatkarimova	
Futbol o'yinida to'pga kalla bilan zarba berish.....	53
Xolmaxmatov Boburjon Musurmon o'g'li	
Использование современных инновационных методов в процессе обучения русскому языку в иноязычных группах высшего образовательного учреждения.....	56
Курбанова Шаира Исмаиловна	
Maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlashda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish ...	60
Kushakova Gulnora Egamkulovna, Muhammadiyeva Shaxzoda Sunnatilla qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda musiqa mashg'ulotlari orqali o'quvchilarning kreativ fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodlari	63
Muminova Feruza Farxodovna	
Alisher Navoiy merosining yoshlar ma'naviy-estetik tarbiyasidagi ahamiyati	70
Qayumxo'jayev Botirxo'ja Ikromxo'ja o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida amaliy topshiriqlar orqali tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish	74
Saidova Dilnoza Maripovna	
К вопросу о классификации современной антиутопии.....	78
Дмитрий Валерьевич Пупонин	
Когнитивная гибкость как фактор психологического благополучия старшеклассников в период адаптации к новым образовательным требованиям	82
Муксинова Динора Азаматовна	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilida ta'lim beruvchi professor-o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini baholash: xalqaro tajribalar qiyosiy tahlili va O'zbekiston amaliyoti	87
Baxtiyarova Muniba Ne'matjon qizi	
Valeologik tarbiya asosida maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarini tayyorlashda innovatsion va raqamli yondashuvlar	92
Berkinova Charos Islomovna	

Grammatik tushunchalarni o'rgatish metodikasi.....	96
N. R. Masharipova	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish va o'quvchilar bilimini baholashda xorijiy tajribalardan foydalanish finlyandiya ta'lim tizimi misolida.....	99
Obidova Muqaddas Ro'ziqulovna	
The Difference Between Androgogy and Pedagogy.....	106
Pardayeva Aziza Rahmatilloevna	
Elektr mashinalari fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari.....	110
Shodiyeva Nozina Shuxrat qizi	
Umumta'lim maktablarida direktor o'rinbosarlarining aksiologik yondashuv asosida boshqaruv funksiyalari va vakolatlari hamda maktablarda ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	113
Toxirov Botirjon G'ofurjon o'g'li	
Ispan tili darslarida kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirish usullari	119
Tursunqulov Sanjar Dilmurod o'g'li, Shukurullayeva Feruza Dilmurodovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatida yetishtiriladigan ingichka tolali paxta navlarining qo'llanilishi	124
Ubaydullayeva Komila Bozor qizi	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda empatiya hissini shakllantirishning nazariy asosi	127
Xolmirzayeva Gulbahor Bahodirovna	

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ANDROGOGY AND PEDAGOGY

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Abstract: This article examines the fundamental differences and interconnections between pedagogy and andragogy within the context of modern education. It analyzes key theoretical perspectives and highlights how teaching approaches vary depending on learners' age, experience, and level of autonomy. The study is based on analytical and synthetic methods, involving a detailed review of works by leading scholars in the field of education. The findings reveal that pedagogy is primarily teacher-centred, while andragogy emphasizes learner independence, intrinsic motivation, and experiential learning. The article concludes that an integrated application of both approaches is essential for effective and flexible educational practice.

Key words: Pedagogy, andragogy, adult learning, teaching methods, learner autonomy, intrinsic motivation, education theory.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada pedagogika va andragogika o'rtasidagi asosiy farqlar hamda o'zaro bog'liqliklar zamonaviy ta'lim kontekstida tahlil qilinadi. Unda ta'lim yondashuvlari o'quvchilarning yoshi, tajribasi va mustaqillik darajasiga qarab qanday farqlanishi ilmiy asosda yoritib beriladi. Tadqiqot tahlil va sintez metodlariga asoslanib, ta'lim sohasidagi yetakchi olimlar ishlari asosida olib borildi. Natijalar pedagogikaning asosan o'qituvchi markazli ekanligini, andragogika esa o'quvchi mustaqilligi, ichki motivatsiya va tajribaga asoslangan o'rganishni ustuvor qo'yishini ko'rsatadi. Maqolada samarali ta'limni tashkil etish uchun har ikkala yondashuvni uyg'unlashtirish zarurligi xulosa qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagogika, andragogika, kattalar ta'limi, o'qitish metodlari, o'quvchi mustaqilligi, ichki motivatsiya, ta'lim nazariyasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются основные различия и взаимосвязи между педагогикой и андрагогией в контексте современного образования. Анализируются ключевые теоретические подходы и показывается, как методы обучения различаются в зависимости от возраста, опыта и уровня самостоятельности обучающихся. Исследование основано на методах анализа и синтеза с использованием трудов ведущих ученых в области образования. Результаты показывают, что педагогика является преимущественно ориентированной на преподавателя, тогда как андрагогика акцентирует внимание на самостоятельности обучающихся, внутренней мотивации и обучении на основе опыта. В статье делается вывод о необходимости интеграции обоих подходов для повышения эффективности образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: Педагогика, андрагогика, обучение взрослых, методы обучения, самостоятельность обучающихся, внутренняя мотивация, теория образования.

INTRODUCTION

Since the concept of andragogy entered the scene in the English-speaking world around 1970, andragogical literature has contained quite a number of comparisons of pedagogy and andragogy^[1]. This historical emergence marked a significant shift in how educators and researchers began to conceptualize learning processes across different age groups, especially distinguishing between child-centered and adult-centered approaches. Over time, the theoretical foundations of pedagogy, traditionally associated with teaching children, were critically examined in relation to andragogy, which emphasizes the unique needs and characteristics of adult learners. Scholars have increasingly explored how these two approaches differ in terms of learner autonomy, motivation, experience, and instructional strategies, leading to a broader understanding of effective teaching methodologies. The growing body of literature reflects an ongoing effort to define clear boundaries as well as overlaps between these concepts, particularly in the context of lifelong learning and higher education. As a result, the comparison between pedagogy and andragogy has become a central theme in educational discourse, shaping both theoretical discussions and practical applications in diverse learning environments.

It has become standard practice in adult education to oppose - or at least compare - pedagogy and andragogy^[2]. This comparison is often used as a framework to better understand how teaching methods can be adapted to suit learners of different ages, backgrounds, and levels of experience. In many cases, pedagogy is characterized by a teacher-centered approach where learners are dependent on the instructor, whereas andragogy promotes a learner-centered model that encourages independence and self-direction. Such distinctions have led educators to reconsider traditional classroom practices and incorporate more flexible, interactive, and experience-based strategies in adult education settings. Furthermore, the contrast between these two approaches has contributed to the development of innovative teaching models that integrate elements of both pedagogy and andragogy to maximize learning outcomes. Therefore, examining the differences and similarities between pedagogy and andragogy remains essential for understanding modern educational practices and improving the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes.

METHOD

In this study, analytical and synthetic methods were selected as the primary research approaches in order to ensure a comprehensive and systematic investigation of the differences between pedagogy and andragogy. The analytical method enabled a detailed examination of existing theories, concepts, and arguments presented in the literature, allowing for a critical evaluation of how various scholars interpret and differentiate these two educational approaches. At the same time, the method of synthesis was applied to integrate diverse perspectives and findings into a coherent framework, thereby providing a more holistic understanding of the topic. In particular, we decided to study and analyze the works of Svein Loeng, Finger, M., & Asún, J. M., Ozuah, P. O., Gehring, T., Fatma Tezcan, Holmes, G., & Abington-Cooper, M., Glassner, A., & Back, S., Knowles, M. S., and Tough, A. M., as these scholars have made significant contributions to the field of adult education and learning theories. Their publications were carefully reviewed in order to identify key similarities, differences, and evolving trends in the interpretation of pedagogy and andragogy. Through this process, reliable data and relevant theoretical insights were gathered to support a deeper and more structured exploration of the research problem.

Furthermore, the research process involved an extensive search for academic sources, including journal articles, books, and credible online materials, to ensure the validity and depth of the study. The selected authors were not only read but also critically analyzed in terms of their methodologies, assumptions, and conclusions regarding teaching and learning processes. By applying analytical thinking, we were able to break down complex ideas into smaller components, making it easier to compare different viewpoints and identify underlying patterns. Subsequently, synthesis allowed us to combine these fragmented insights into a unified interpretation that reflects the broader significance of pedagogy and andragogy in modern education. This combined methodological approach also helped to highlight gaps in the literature and suggest potential areas for further research. As a result, the study aims to provide a well-grounded and in-depth understanding of the topic by relying on both critical analysis and integrative synthesis of authoritative academic sources.

RESULTS

It should be noted that pedagogy is fundamentally a teacher-centred model, where the teacher determines what will be learned, how it will be learned, when it will be learned, and if it has been learned^[3]. This is commonly considered to be in contrast to andragogy, referred to as the education of adults. Adults bring valuable experiential knowledge with them and have community-oriented aspirations^[4].

The degree of dependence, which is high in the first years of an individual's life, decreases towards adolescence and then leaves its place to self-directed behavior to a large extent. In this sense, psychological adulthood means being responsible for one's own life^[5].

Pedagogy was based on the transmission of knowledge. Adult learners seemed to be dissatisfied with pedagogical teaching strategies, such as lectures, assigned readings, drills, quizzes, note memorising and examinations^[6].

While establishing a learning model for adults, Knowles, in his early work, adopted the idea that the andragogical model is the antithesis of the pedagogical model and discussed the andragogical approach based on pedagogy^[7].

There are better learners in the andragogical model on the school education level; however, it is the educators' responsibility to use pedagogical and andragogical models in a learning environment. Adults are stimulated by intrinsic factors such as personal interests and goals, rather than extrinsic ones such as praise and grades^[8].

These findings indicate that the nature of learning significantly changes with age, experience, and psychological development. They also show that motivation, responsibility, and autonomy play a crucial role in adult education. Overall, the collected data highlight clear distinctions as well as certain connections between pedagogical and andragogical approaches.

The results clearly demonstrate that pedagogy is primarily teacher-centred, which means that learners have a relatively passive role in the educational process, especially during early stages of development. This aligns with the idea that children require structured guidance, as they lack sufficient experience and independence to direct their own learning effectively. In contrast, andragogy emphasizes learner autonomy, which becomes increasingly important as individuals grow older and gain more life experience. The findings suggest that the shift from dependence to self-direction is not only educational but also psychological in nature, reflecting broader developmental changes. Therefore, the distinction between pedagogy and andragogy can be understood as a natural progression rather than a strict opposition. This interpretation highlights the importance of adapting teaching strategies according to the learner's developmental stage.

Furthermore, the role of experience in adult learning is a key factor that differentiates andragogy from pedagogy. Adults bring valuable experiential knowledge with them and have community-oriented aspirations, which significantly influence how they perceive and engage with new information. Unlike children, who rely heavily on teachers as the primary source of knowledge, adults tend to integrate new learning with their existing experiences. This makes the learning process more interactive, reflective, and meaningful in adult education contexts. The dissatisfaction of adult learners with traditional pedagogical methods, such as lectures and memorization, further supports the need for more flexible and participatory approaches. Consequently, educators must design learning environments that acknowledge and utilize the prior experiences of adult learners.

Another important aspect highlighted in the findings is the difference in motivation between children and adults. Adults are stimulated by intrinsic factors such as personal interests and goals, rather than extrinsic ones such as praise and grades, which are more effective for younger learners. This indicates that adult education should focus on relevance, practicality, and personal development rather than external rewards. The concept of self-directed learning also plays a significant role here, as adults tend to take responsibility for their own educational progress. This reinforces the idea that andragogy is better suited for mature learners who are capable of managing their own learning processes. As a result, motivation becomes a central element in distinguishing between pedagogical and andragogical approaches.

Finally, the discussion of Knowles' perspective reveals that the relationship between pedagogy and andragogy is more complex than a simple dichotomy. While he initially presented andragogy as the antithesis of pedagogy, later interpretations suggest that both approaches can and should be used together in educational practice. There are better learners in the andragogical model on the school education level; however, it is the educators' responsibility to use pedagogical and andragogical models in a learning environment. This implies that effective teaching requires flexibility and the ability to combine different methods depending on the context and learners' needs. The integration of both approaches allows for a more balanced and inclusive educational system. Therefore, rather than viewing pedagogy and andragogy as opposing models, they should be seen as complementary frameworks that together enhance the overall learning experience.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the comparative analysis of pedagogy and andragogy demonstrates that these two approaches represent not opposing but evolving dimensions of the teaching-learning process shaped by learners' developmental, psychological, and experiential characteristics. Pedagogy, with its structured and teacher-centred orientation, remains essential in guiding learners who require direction, foundational knowledge, and external motivation, particularly in early stages of education. In contrast, andragogy reflects the shift toward autonomy, self-direction, and intrinsic motivation that characterizes adult learners, emphasizing the importance of experience, relevance, and personal responsibility in the learning process. The findings confirm that as individuals mature, their learning preferences and needs transform significantly, requiring educators to adopt more flexible and learner-centred strategies. At the same time, the research highlights that neither approach is sufficient on its own, as effective education depends on the thoughtful integration of both pedagogical and andragogical principles. Therefore, modern educational practice should move beyond rigid distinctions and instead focus on creating adaptive learning environments that respond to the diverse needs of learners. Ultimately, recognizing the complementary nature of pedagogy and andragogy provides a stronger theoretical and practical foundation for improving teaching effectiveness and fostering meaningful, lifelong learning.

References:

1. Svein Loeng. Pedagogy and Andragogy in Comparison – Conceptions and Perspectives. *Andragoška spoznanja/ Studies in Adult Education and Learning*, 2023, 29(2), 39-52 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4312/as/11482> file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/Pedagogy_and_Andragogy_in_Comparison_-_Conceptions.pdf
2. F Ozuah, P. O. (2005). First, there was pedagogy and then came andragogy. *The Einstein Journal of Biology and Medicine*, 21, 83–87.
3. Gehring, T. (2000). A compendium of material on the pedagogy-andragogy issue. *Journal of Correctional Education*, 51(1), 151–163.
4. atma Tezcan. Andragogy or Pedagogy: Views of Young Adults on the Learning Environment. *International Education Studies*; Vol. 15, No. 1; 2022 ISSN 1913-9020 E-ISSN 1913-9039 Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education. file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/Andragogy_or_Pedagogy_Views_of_Young_Adults_on_the.pdf
5. Holmes, G., & Abington-Cooper, M. (2000). Pedagogy vs. andragogy: A false dichotomy? *The Journal of Technology Studies*, 26(2), 50–55. <https://doi.org/10.21061/jots.v26i2.a.8>
6. Glassner, A., & Back, S. (2020). Three “Gogies”: Pedagogy, andragogy, heutagogy. In *Exploring Heutagogy in Higher Education* (pp. 59-74). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4144-5_5
7. Knowles, M. S. (1996). Yetişkin öğrenenler gözardı edilen bir kesim [Adult learners a neglected species] (S. Ayhan, Trans.). Ankara: Ankara Üniversitesi Basımevi.
8. Tough, A. M. (1979). *The adult's learning projects: A fresh approach to theory and practice in adult learning*. University of Toronto Press.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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